

steel section under cyclic loading, *Journal of Constructional Steel Research*, No.61, pp.863-81.

9. Li, L., Sakai, J., Matsui, C., 2003, Seismic behavior of steel encased reinforced concrete beam–columns, In: *Proceedings of the international conference on advances in structures.*, p. 1201–7.

10. Bayrak, O., Sheikh, SA., 2001, Plastic hinge analysis, *Journal of Structural Engineering*;127(9):1092–100.

11. Ellobody, E., Young, B., 2006, Design and behaviour of concrete-filled cold-formed stainless steel tube columns, *Engineering Structures*;28(5):716–28.

12. Ellobody, E., Young, B., 2006, Nonlinear analysis of concrete-filled steel SHS and RHS columns, *Thin walled Structures*;44(8):919–30.

13. Saberi AA, Ahmadi H, Sedaghat Shayegan D, Amirkardoust, A. PREDICTION OF ELECTRICITY CONSUMPTION USING THREE META-HEURISTIC ALGORITHMS, *Int J Optim Civil Eng* 2023; 13(1): 111-125.

14. Sedaghat Shayegan D, Lork A, Hashemi AH. Optimum cost design of reinforced concrete slabs using Mouth Brooding Fish (MBF) algorithm, *J Appl Eng Sci* 2020; 10(23): 95-100.

15. Sedaghat Shayegan D, Lork A, Hashemi AH. Mouth Brooding Fish algorithm for cost optimization of reinforced concrete one-way ribbed slabs, *Int J Optim Civil Eng* 2019; 9(3): 411-22.

16. Sedaghat Shayegan D. Optimum cost design of reinforced concrete slabs using a metaheuristic algorithm, *Int J Optim Civil Eng* 2022; 12(4): 545-55

17. Sedaghat Shayegan D, Lork A, Hashemi AH. A new hybrid algorithm for cost optimization of waffle slab, *Slov J Civil Eng* 2020; 28(3): 40-6.

18. Sedaghat Shayegan D, Lork A, Hashemi SAH. The assessment of fragility curves of the Application of diagonal and chevron viscous damper in steel structures using a metaheuristic algorithm for modification of ground motions, *J Struct Construct Eng* 2021; 7(4): 100-15.

19. A, ghadiri, D. Sedaghat Shayegan and A. Amirkardoust, “Multi-objective firefly optimization algorithm for construction site layout planning”, *Iranian Journal of optimization*, Volume 14, Issue 4, December 2022. Chu H, Hwang GJ. A Delphi-based approach to developing expert systems with the cooperation of multiple experts, *Expert Syst Applicat* 2008; 34(4): 2826-40.

PRINCIPLES OF CONSTRUCTION A CONTROL AND REGULATION SYSTEM FOR A TECHNOLOGICAL COMPLEX, INCLUDING A VACUUM BLOCK

Hesenli V.,

Student, department of Electronics and Automation

Melikov E.

Associate professor, department of Electronics and Automation

Abstract

The article proposes conceptual principles for constructing an automated control system for the atmospheric-vacuum complex of a primary oil refining unit. The developed adaptive control system for the complex under study is presented in the form of a hierarchical structure, at the upper level of which the optimal operating parameters for the technological process are calculated, and at the lower level, mainly, the optimal regulation of technological parameters in the main apparatuses of the complex is carried out, ensuring the oil fractions production with the required values of quality indicators.

Keywords: distillation column, technological complex, control system, target product, regulation system, optimal control.

There are a considerable number of scientific publications devoted to the development of mathematical models, methods and control algorithms, as well as the construction of control systems for the main technological apparatuses of oil refinery and petrochemical plants [1÷5]. Most of these works took into account the deterministic nature of the technological processes occurring in these apparatuses.

Based on a complex of probabilistic-mathematical models that take into account the random nature of the input flows for a given technological object, the article proposes the principles for developing an optimal automated control system for a technological complex (atmospheric and vacuum blocks), which is a system with a two-level hierarchical structure that operates in dialog mode. The functional structure of the two-level control system for the considered technological unit of the investigated installation is shown in Figure 1.

At the upper level of the proposed control system, the optimal operating modes are determined for any values of the quantitative and qualitative indicators of crude oil entering the inlet of the electric desalination installation, Atmospheric vacuum tube type unit, which ensures the production of light oil fractions in distillation columns K-1, K-2, K-10, meeting the requirements of the standard for the depth of processing and the quality of oil fractions.

The optimization criterion chosen at this level is achieved with the help of the mathematical models constructed set of a deterministic and probabilistic nature, as well as an optimization algorithm based on the decomposition principle. In the case under consideration, depending on the amount and type of crude oil received for processing, the technical and economic indicators of the primary oil refining technological process are also calculated.

Figure 1. Functional structure of the control system for the technological complex of the installation (atmospheric and vacuum blocks)

At the lower level of the developed control system hierarchical structure to solve the tasks set in the system, the following is directly carried out: collection of primary information, operational identification through control channels, optimal automatic synthesis of temperature parameters and the problem of automatic control in distillation columns K-1, K-2 and K-10.

At the same time, the functioning at each level of the proposed optimal control system is carried out in an interactive mode.

In general, the functioning of the constructed automatic control system can be represented as follows: when switching to new operating modes or when changing the flow rate of crude oil supplied for processing, as well as when changing the main quality indicators, these mathematical models are adapted, if necessary, after studying the adequacy of mathematical models, developed at the upper level of the system under consideration.

In the article, in order to stabilize the parameters of the studied technological processes optimal operating mode at the lower level of the optimal control system, a self-regulating adaptive control system for the temperature coordinates of the distillation column under consideration is proposed. Let us consider the foregoing on the example of a self-adjusting system for the adaptive control according to the temperature coordinates of the K-10 vacuum column.

It is known that one of the main issues in the control of a technological installation for primary oil refining is the development of an optimal automatic control system that is most resistant to changing disturbances. The development of such an effective management system requires the use of new additional regulation means at its lower level. Therefore, in order to eliminate the lack of information in existing control systems, it is proposed to use combined automatic control systems to build a self-adjusting adaptive control system.

The main essence of the operation principle for the mentioned automatic control systems is that the effect of disturbing influences resulting from frequent changes in the quantitative and qualitative indicators of raw materials, that is, fuel oil entering the distillation (vacuum) column under consideration, on the quality indicators of light oil products produced from the required plate, is provided by the necessary compensation due to a proportional simultaneous change in the same selected plate of temperature or irrigation flow.

Therefore, such an automatic control system involves the addition of a certain correction signal (P_k) to the built-in system to compensate for small changes in the reflux flow rate and the temperature of the vacuum column. Currently, the value of the correction signal (P_k) added to the setpoint of the temperature controller (TC) used to control the temperature of the vacuum column is proportional to the change in the flow rate of the irrigation included in the desired plate (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Combined temperature control system in the vacuum column K-10

Figure 2. Combined temperature control system in the vacuum column K-10

But in the second case, this correction signal is carried out in proportion to the change in its temperature in the required plate of the distillation column.

The correction, determined depending on the disturbing influences on the inlet of the vacuum column, makes it possible to calculate a new set point.

This provides a prompt response even to minor changes in disturbing influences and subsequently leads to the prompt achievement of optimal operating modes for the technological installation under consideration at minimal cost.

The flow rate measured by the irrigation flow sensor (FE) is transmitted to the Computing Block (CB) of the technological system. Here, in this block, a correction signal is determined, applied to the adaptive thermostat, based on a comparison of the current irrigation flow rate with the previous one. Then the signal received at the output of the adaptive temperature controller is sent to the actuator (A) installed on the irrigation line. When measuring the current temperature value on the required (selected) plate of the considered distillation column, a temperature sensor (TE) is used.

In the case of irrigation flow control (Figure 3), the current temperature value measured by the temperature sensor (TE) is transmitted to the CB. In the specified

computing unit, depending on the temperature difference at the moment t and at the previous moment ($t-1$), the necessary corrective signal is determined, which is then transmitted to the adaptive flow controller (FC). The obtained current irrigation value in the specified combined automatic control system is measured using an irrigation flow sensor.

The functioning of the built combined automatic control system is carried out as follows: as a result of an increase in the consumption of raw materials (fuel oil) supplied to the vacuum column, the volume of the hot mass rising upwards also increases inside the column. All this leads to an increase in the irrigation flow rate and, in turn, to an increase in the required corrective signal in the newly built automatic control system.

Thus, this will lead to some increase in temperature in the selected plate of the vacuum column and, at the same time, to an increase in the flow rate for irrigation supplied to this place. In the newly presented automatic control system, the effect of temperature increase on the quality parameters of the target product obtained from the selected plate, and the effect of increasing irrigation flow on these indicators are mutual, since, in the end, the quality indicators of the target product produced will remain partially stable

when compared with conventional automatic control system.

Similarly, a reduction in fuel oil consumption ultimately leads to a decrease in the temperature in the considered plate and irrigation consumption. Since the impact of these reductions on the quality of the target product produced offset each other, these indicators will remain stable.

From the foregoing, we can conclude that in both cases, stable maintenance of the vacuum column temperature regime is one of the important and basic conditions for the effective operation of the presented automatic control systems. Therefore, due to various technical reasons arising from the control point of view, it is advisable to use these automatic control systems in changing and unstable operating modes.

Thus, in the presented article, a combined temperature control system was built on the selected plate of the vacuum column, as well as the irrigation flow rate, which ensures more efficient and stable operation of the automatic control system.

References

1. Goodvin G. C., Grabe S. F., Salgado M. E.. Control System Design, Prentice Hall, 2004, pp. 23-39.
2. Wilde D.J., Beightler C.S., Johnson D.B. Foundations of Optimization Prentice-Hall. England cliffs, New Jersey, 2012, 201 p.
3. Efendiev I.R., Guseinov I.A., Melikov E.E., Kurbanov Z.G., Efendiev A.I. Nonstationary Multistage Process Control in the Petrochemical Industry. Journal of Computer and Systems Sciences International, Pleiades Publishing, Ltd., Vol. 53, No. 4, 2014, pp. 556-564.
4. Parks P.S., Scaufelberger W., Schmid Chr., Unbenhauen H. Application of adaptive control systems. Methods and application in adaptive control, berl. Heudalb., N.Y.: Spring – Verlag, 2005, hh. 181-193.
5. Melikov E.A., Maharramova T.M. Energy saving system in vacuum unit. Ekoenergetics, Baku, 2022, №3, pp. 8-12.